

Geometric Diversity versus Frequency Diversity

An Imaging Example

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Introduction

In classical radar, frequency diversity offers one method of obtaining additional information about targets. With the most basic form of frequency diversity, namely increased bandwidth, high range resolution is afforded to the user. Geometric diversity can also offer the potential for increased resolution, and is the multi-static dual to frequency diversity (increased bandwidth) in classical mono-static radar. In the extreme case, 360 degrees of geometric diversity (tomography) offers sub-wavelength resolution, even under the monochromatic assumption.

Operational constraints can limit the system performance. Frequency diversity and geometric diversity can be used in various combinations to obtain the best image under these constraints. For example, frequency allocation can limit the available bandwidth. Geometric diversity with a single or multiple narrowband signals can provide the required system performance.

Imaging performance can be evaluated using two factors: resolution and target dynamic range. Resolution is the ability to distinguish two closely separated targets and dynamic range is the ability to determine the presence of a ‘weak’ target in the presence of a ‘strong’ target.

Geometric Diversity

In image processing, the radar data samples are mapped onto a polar grid in the spatial Fourier domain [1 – 6]. The positions of the transmitter and receiver along with the signal’s instantaneous frequency determines the Fourier space sample position. This relation is illustrated in Figure 1. A bi-static sensor configuration is shown with a bi-static angle (B), \mathbf{u}_B is the bi-static bisector. This geometry and signal frequency maps into the Fourier space sample given by the vector \mathbf{F} . As shown, the sample position lies along the bi-static bisector with a magnitude proportional to the instantaneous frequency scaled by $\cos(B/2)$.

Figure 1: Sensor Geometry & Fourier Space Relationship

Figure 2 illustrates a typical Fourier space sampling as provided by a mono-static SAR. As shown, the samples in the radial dimension straddle a term proportional to the carrier frequency and have an extent proportional to the signal bandwidth. Samples in the angular dimension correspond to pulse numbers of the coherent processing interval. In the mono-static case, the angular extent of the samples is the same as the angular aperture created by the synthetic aperture.

Figure 2: Fourier Space Sampling & Scene Resolution

Recall that the image resolution is inversely proportional to the size of the region of Fourier space sampled. The unambiguous scene size is inversely proportional to the Fourier space sampling frequency.

In the spatial Fourier domain radial band limiting is due to the finite bandwidth of the transmitted pulse and angular band limiting is due to the finite diversity of look angles. With variations of frequency and angular diversity the spatial Fourier domain can be sampled in a variety of ways. This spatial Fourier domain sampling impacts the resulting image's resolution. Higher resolution

is achieved with greater diversity, be it frequency, angular or some combination of both. Image resolution is inversely proportional to the size of the region of Fourier space sampled. Figure 3 illustrates, by way of four examples, how different bi-static geometries and waveforms map into Fourier space. In example 1, a fixed bi-static geometry and a wideband waveform result in Fourier space sampling along a radial line, at the bi-static bisector. In example 2, a fixed frequency (CW) waveform is used as the receiver is moved in a circle about the origin. The resulting Fourier space sampling is a circle whose center is offset from the origin. In example 3, a wideband waveform is used as the receiver is moved in a circle about the origin. The resulting Fourier space sampling is a combination of the results of examples 1 and 2. For completeness, example 4 shows the case of a wideband waveform and a mono-static geometry. The resulting Fourier space sampling has a donut shape. The typical mono-static SAR doesn't fly a circular flight path around a scene, but instead flies a straight line path, the resulting Fourier space sampling is highlighted as a wedge of the donut.

Figure 3: Sensor Geometry & Fourier Space Relationship Examples

Resolution is a function of the bandwidth available in the 2-D Fourier space. The conventional SAR resolution formulas are approximations to this for the limited cases of small apertures and percent bandwidths. The narrowband, wide angle multi-static imaging achieves the resolution of wideband, narrow angle SAR systems by trading frequency for spatial diversity. The resolution limit for this system is about one third of a wavelength. A comparison of Fourier space sampling provided by mono, bi and multi-static SAR and their corresponding resolution is illustrated in Figure 4. The colored area represents the region of Fourier space sampled. The simplified resolution formulas for small aperture and percent bandwidth are given for the mono and bi-static cases. For the bi-static case, assume a pseudo-mono-static geometry with the transmitter is in a fixed position and the receiver is forming an aperture the same as the mono-static case. In the bi-static case, the angular sampling is compressed, compared to the mono-static, due to sampling occurring on the bi-static bisector. This results in loss in cross range resolution. In the

multi-static case, a circular region could potentially be sampled. The radius of this circle is proportional to the highest frequency used and the resulting image has a resolution of a third of a wavelength of this frequency. To compare the resolution capabilities of these sensor configurations, consider UWB mono-static SAR with a 50% bandwidth has a range resolution of λ and a pixel area of λ^2 . The multi-static SAR with a range resolution of $\lambda/3$ has a pixel area of $\lambda^2/9$, a 9.5 dB improvement over mono-static.

Figure 4: Comparison of Fourier Space Sampling

Two Platform Circular SAR

Multistatic SAR (Figure 4, right hand image) has excellent resolution but requires many transmitter and receiver locations. An approach to obtain similar resolution but with significantly fewer assets is proposed – Two Platform Circular SAR. Separate transmitter and receive platforms circle the region of interest at different angular velocities flying at different speeds and/or at different radii. For example the transmitter could orbit the region with angular velocity ω_T , while the receiver’s angular velocity is $\omega_R = -10 * \omega_T$. Depending on bandwidth this would result in multiple rings of coverage in Fourier space similar to the rings of Figure 3/Examples 2 (narrow band) or 3 (wide band). Due to the motion of the transmitter, the rings would be offset in azimuth and distorted (See figure 5). Although not fully filling the Fourier space similar to Multistatic SAR, much of the region will be covered yielding similar resolution.

Figure 5: Fourier Space Coverage for Two Platform Circular SAR

Figure 6 shows the evolution of the image development for this concept as the transmitter completes one revolution (and the receiver completes ten revolutions). The simple image consists of four point targets (two on the x-axis at $\lambda/3$, $-\lambda/3$ and two on the y-axis at $\lambda/3$, $-\lambda/3$). The targets become distinguishable after the transmitter has completed one-half of an orbit and the image sidelobes improve as the transmitter completes an orbit. This amount of spatial diversity reduces the requirements for frequency diversity (bandwidth). Figure 7 compares the images for 10% bandwidth and 0.1% bandwidth. The resolution is almost exactly the same; the higher bandwidth has slightly better image sidelobes. The resolution is close to that of the Multistatic SAR approach with its large number of transmitters and receivers.

Figure 6: Image Evolution

Figure 7: Bandwidth Comparison

The excellent imaging performance of the Two Platform Circular SAR with a narrowband waveform provides a capability for imaging in an environment with limited frequency allocation. Multiple narrowband tones are being investigated to reduce image sidelobes and thus to improve target dynamic range. Figures 8 & 9 illustrate the imaging performance with two narrowband tones: (a) at λ & at $0.9*\lambda$ and (b) at λ & at $0.5*\lambda$ respectively. The two-tone case with 10% difference in frequency improves dynamic range slightly while having only a small impact on

resolution. The two-tone case with 50% difference in frequency significantly improves dynamic range while degrading resolution. Resolution and dynamic range can both be preserved by processing the three configurations (single tone, both two-tone) in parallel and using the appropriate configuration depending on the objective (good resolution between targets of similar cross-section, detection of a weak target in the presence of a strong target).

Figure 8

Summary

Combining frequency diversity with geometric diversity provides the system designer with much greater flexibility to respond to operational constraints (frequency allocation, other interfering systems). The cost of this flexibility does not have to be overwhelming (Two Platform Circular SAR compared to Multistatic SAR).